
Electron Identification at PHENIX

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Abstract

This document outlines the procedure for identifying electrons within the PHENIX framework.

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1 Introduction

The analysis modules within the PHENIX framework are submitted to the CVS directory and are run using the taxi. In this document, detailed instructions for writing a code for identifying electrons, submitting the analysis module and working the way through taxi is provided.

It is not advisable to work in the home directory due to space restrictions. Hence, once the PHENIX account is set up, please request for space on the working group disk (e.g. PLHF). This is where the taxi output is written.

2 Electron identification

Within the PHENIX detector setup, information from the Drift Chamber (DC), the Ring Cherenkov detector (RICH) and the Electromagnetic Calorimeter (EMCal) is used to identify electrons.

The most important criteria are:

- The quality of the track which is given by the hit pattern in the DC.

$$\text{quality} = 63 \parallel 51 \parallel 31$$

- Minimum momentum for a reliable reconstruction of the track.

$$p_T > 0.15 \text{ GeV}$$

- The z extent of the DC.

$$|zed| < 75 \text{ cm}$$

- The number of photo-tubes fired in RICH.

$$n0 > 0$$

- The distance between the ring center and track projection in RICH.

$$disp < 5$$

- The ratio of energy (from EMCal) to momentum (from DC) of a given track ($ecore/p$). Sometimes, it is preferred to signalize this cut to make it momentum independent and, hence, increase the purity (dep).

$$ecore/p > 0.5 \quad \text{or} \quad -2 < dep < 5$$

- Shower shape in the EMCal

$$\chi^2/npe0 < 10$$

- The probability of the shower in the associated subcluster being electromagnetic.

$$prob > 0.01$$

- Matching of the track between DC and EMCal. This cut can also be signalized to match within 5 sigma.

$$EMCdz < 20 \text{ cm}; EMCd\phi < 0.05 \quad \text{or} \quad |EMCsdz| < 5; |EMCsd\phi| < 5$$

- DC side = RICH side = PC1 side to avoid side crossing tracks.

Other cuts can be introduced depending on the analysis and the desired purity of the electron candidates.

3 Building the analysis module

The analysis module is a folder containing all the files used to run the code on taxi. The main ingredients are the following:

- `autogen.sh`
- `configure.in`
- `Makefile.am`
- Analysis files in class structure (`*.C` and `*.h` and `*LinkDef.h`)

A ready-to-run explicit example can be found at

`offline/AnalysisTrain/ExampleElectronAnalysis`

and the HPSS snapshot is located at

`/home/roli/ExampleElectronAnlalysis.tar`

`ExampleElectronAnalysis` contains the following files:

- `autogen.sh`
- `configure.in`
- `Makefile.am`
- `RDanalyzer.*`
 - This is the main analyzer file to create TTrees and histograms
- `MyEvent.*`
 - This defines the TTree structure
- `MyAnalysis.C`
 - This is an example to run on the produced TTrees from RDanalyzer.

All analysis modules are available at

<https://www.phenix.bnl.gov/viewvc/viewvc.cgi/phenix/offline/AnalysisTrain/>

To download a module from CVS,

```
cvs checkout offline/AnalysisTrain/ModuleName
```

In this case,

```
ModeuleName = ExampleElectronAnalysis
```

To compile this module and test locally, the executable macro will be required. To retrieve this

```
cvs checkout offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro/Run_ExampleElectron.C
cvs checkout offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro/RunMyMacro.C
```

Only one example data file for each dataset is stored on an accessible disk so as to test the code. In order to run on the entire dataset, taxi needs to be submitted. This will be discussed later.

Before running locally, the module needs to be compiled. Steps to compile and run the example module is outline below:

```
cd offline/AnalysisTrain/ExampleElectronAnalysis
autogen.sh --prefix=$MYINSTALL
make
make install

cd offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro
root -l 'RunMyMacro.C("Run_ExampleElectron.C", "output.root", 20000,
  "Run14AuAu200CAnVXMBP106")'
```

Make sure \$MYINSTALL is predefined. "Run14AuAu200CAnVXMBP106" is the code name defining to the dataset. 20000 is the number of events on which the code is tested. Use 0 to run on the entire file. Each file typically has around 2M events.

4 Committing the module

Before committing files to CVS, the permission needs to be unlocked using

```
klog.krb5
```

The password would be your RCF account password. Once unlocked, new module can be added using

```
cd offline/AnalysisTrain/
cvs add YourModule
cvs update YourModule
cd YourModule
cvs add (each file individually)
cvs commit -m "message" (each file individually)
```

Make sure that autogen.sh and configure.in are executable before uploading to CVS.

```
chmod 755 autogen.sh
chmod 755 configure.in
```

The executable macro accompanying the analysis module should be named Run_YourExecutable.C and is uploaded using

```
cd offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro
cvs add Run_YourExecutable.C
cvs commit -m "message" Run_YourExecutable.C
```

To commit files after editing,

```
cvs commit -m "message" filename
```

It is a good practice to include the changes made in the message.

5 Running taxi

Once the code is tested and committed to CVS, taxi jobs can be submitted. To do this the following website is used.

<https://www.phenix.bnl.gov/WWW/p/draft/anatrain/register/taxiRegForm.html>

The entries in the form is explained below:

- Name : your name
- E-mail : your email address
- Macro name : Run_YourExecutable.C
- Analysis code directories : YourModule
- PWG disk : the working group where you have your directory (e.g. plhf in case of /phenix/plhf/username)
- User name : username
- Select the dataset you would like to run on (In case of the example, select Run14 Au+Au 200GeV Central Arm Pro106(MinBias))
- DST types : Select all applicable (In case of the example CNT and DST_EVE)
- Aggregation : choose Yes if you would like the output to be written out by run number
- Event mixing : depends on your analysis (In this example, No)
- Runnumber list : provide if you can
- Estimated disk space : just an estimate (e.g. 5 GB)

- Additional requests : if you have any

Submit the form when done.

The output from taxi (TTrees/histograms) can be found in

`/phenix/(PWG disk name)/username/taxi`

6 Characteristics plots

Figure 1: Distribution of E/p of electron candidates.

Figure 2: Distribution of n_0 of electron candidates

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the characteristic distribution of E/p and n_0 of electron candidates as seen in Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV.

The PHENIX WIKI would be a good source of details, if needed.